

ODIA DERIVATIONAL MORPHEMES : A GENERAL 'TAG'MODEL FOR RECOGNITION AND PRODUCTION

□ Rudranarayan Mohapatra*

ABSTRACT

In recent past a number of attempt and approach has been followed for the analysis of sub-systems for Generative morphology. Kimmo Koskeniemi (1983)'s two-level morphology approach (word form and lexical units) (Oflazer, 1993), Jappinen's (1984) rule based heuristic approach, Halle's Model (1990), Aronoff's model (1994), Beesley's (1996) finite state transducer specifying legal morpheme sequences of both inflectional and derivational kind, Agirve's (2000) Bas-que, Oflazer Kamel's (2004) Finite State Machine (FSM), Robert Elwell's (2008) syllables and utilizing the surface level clues based Morphological Analyzer for Swahili language, Wukui Zheng's (2012) Morphological analysis using Multidimensional Scaling have proven the potential frameworks in the area of generative morphology and are used for different natural language processing applications but not limited to expert opinion, bibliometrics, text mining and/or multidimensional scaling. Here in this paper we have tried to describe the divisional form and production of Odia Derivational morphemes and its syntactic relationship with TAG Grammar.

Keywords : Derivation, Odia Language, Derivational Morpheme, Reduplication, Tree-Adjoining Grammar (TAG)

1. INTRODUCTION

Morphology, the components of language and languages are a psychological or cognitive property of the human species wherein several subsystems are at work here. Once the articulated sound waves are translated into mental representations of speech sounds, we take these groups of sounds and organize them into meaningful units (called 'morphemes') and words. For example, the word 'speaker' is made up of two meaningful bits: 'speak' and the suffix '-er'. The study of this micro-structural level of language is called morphology. The study of morphology is as old as the discipline of linguistics itself. The ancient grammatical treatise 'Astadhyayi' written by the Sanskrit grammarian Panini was devoted to the in-depth study of morphology. The study of morphology can also be witnessed in the ancient Greco-Roman period and within the Arabic linguistic tradition.

Investigation into the theory of syntax became

predominant primarily due to scholarship of Noam Chomsky and his colleagues, beginning in the 1950s. Such investigation continues through to the present. Over time, different versions of the overall theory of generative grammar have developed; including but not limited to Transformational Grammar (TG), Transformational Generative Grammar, Standard Theory, Extended Standard Theory, Government and Binding Theory (GB), Principles and Parameters approach (P&P) and Minimalism (MP). The overall goal of generative morphology is to model these procedures and formalizations through a set of formal morphological rules and representations.

2. O DIA L AN G U A G E A N D I T S M O R P H O L O G I C A L P H E N O M E N A

Odia is an Eastern Indian language belonging to the Indo-Aryan language family with a relatively little influence of Persian, Arabic and Mundari family. Dealing with agglutinative languages like Odia, its generative

*P.G. Department of Odia, Utkal University, Vanivihar, Bhubaneswar, Odisha

Morphology plays a vital role as its usages of classifiers, and feature base agreement, and semantic contextual agreement etc. make it morphologically complex. In Odia language, a morpheme termed as: 'Rüpéma' is the most minuscule meaningful constituent which combines and synthesizes the phonemes into a meaningful expression through its morpheme's form & structure. As the example in two words, /'bi-jaatiyataa/ (anti-nationalist)', /jaatiyataa-baada/ (patriotism), /jaati/ (caste/nation), the free morpheme and "yataa" one of the bound morpheme having no sense independently, /bi/ (anti), /baada/ (ism) etc. are examples of independent morphemes with their meanings. Odia is like other languages of the world in which two major types of morphemes can be identified: free and bound. From a functional point of view, Odia also exhibits inflectional and derivational morphemes.

Traditional grammars of Odia language classify the derived forms in Odia into two categories- Krudantas and Taddhitas. Krudantas are the adjectives, adverbs and

nouns derived from verbs, while Taddhitas are nouns, adjectives and adverbs derived from words of any category other than verb. This is also accompanied by inflectional processes which help lend the words features of gender, number, person, case, tense, aspect and modality. Odia language added three types of morphemes (prefix, suffix & infix) with its root for its derivational lexicon.

3. DERIVATION AND ODIA DERIVATIONAL MORPHEMES

Derivation is concerned with the structure of the stem, a derivational morpheme is affixed to the word stem (the form a root takes when a derivational morpheme is attached to it), and in order to add meaning to it and thereby derives a new word. However, at the time of generation, it sometimes also possesses the compounding behavior in which a stem is formed from two roots, with the resultant stem belonging to the form class of at least one of the constituent roots. Table '1' below provides some examples from Odia.

Word -1	Word-2	Compound	Gloss
Chhapara (thatch)[N]	/Ghara/(house) [N]	/chhapara-ghara/	thatch house
/Thanda/ (cold)[A]	/Pani/ (water)[N]	/thanda-pani/	cold-water
/kaatha/ (wooden)[N]	/Ghoda/ (horse)[N]	/katha-ghoda/	wooden-horse
/Mendhaa/ (sheep) [N]	/Shaala/ house [N]	/mendhaa-shaala/	sheep-house
/aamba/ (mango)[N]	/toTaa/(garden)[N]	/aambatoTaa/	mango-garden

Table 1: Odia Derived words through Compounding

Except the compounding, the basic function of the derivational process in Odia is to enable speakers to create new lexemes in the language. They are added to the existing roots or stems and expanded them with a new semantic connotation. Usually, the open class of words is extended by means of word-formation. Since, the closed class of words is function class of words; therefore, they

cannot produce new words. Bauer (2001) states "A derivational morpheme is the morpheme which produces a new lexeme from a base." Derivational morphemes are generally derived or create new words by either changing the meaning or the part of speech or both. Below in 'Table 2' we can look some derivation processes and word formation in Odia.

Prefix	Noun	Suffix	Derivation	Gloss
....	/muni/ (sage)[N]	/-a/	/mauna/	silent [N/A]
....	/bigyana/ (science)[N]	/-ika/	/baigyanika/	scientist [N]
	/michha/ (lie)	/-uaa/	/michhuuaa/	liar [N]
/ana-/	/naati/ (grand-son)	/-aa/	/ananaatiaa/	The man having no grand-son

Table 2: Odia derived words through 'derivation'

3.1. REDUPLICATION

Reduplication is another morphological process in which a part of a root or a copy of the entire root is added to the root. According to Laurel J. Brinton (1991: 91),

“Reduplication is a process similar to derivation, in which the initial syllable or the entire word is doubled, exactly or with a slight morphological change.” Reduplication as a type of word formation is prevalent in Odia.’

Word-1	Word-2	Reduplication	Gloss
/paDhu/ (to read) [V]	/paDhu/ (to read) [V]	/paDhu-paDhu/	‘having read’
/kahu/ (to speak) [V]	/kahu/ (to speak) [V]	/kahu-kahu/	‘having spoken’
/shunu/ (to hear) [V]	/shunu/ (to hear) [V]	/shunu-shunu/	‘having heard’
/chak/ (shine) [N]	/chak/ (shine) [N]	/chak-chak/	‘shining’

Table 3': Some basic forms.

The classification of reduplicative constructions can be based on the process of repetition of elements of the base or root form. Following from this, we can distinguish between complete and partial reduplication in

Odia. The Complete reduplication is one where the root form is exactly repeated, no addition or modification occurs in reduplicated form. In other words, we could call this process 'repetition.' For example:

(a)	/Jaka/ (glitter)	/Jaka-jaka/	glittering
(b)	/ghara/ (house)	/Ghara-ghara/	many houses
(c)	/Bada/ (big)	/Bada-bada/	Big -&-big
(d)	/chapi/ (controlling)	/chapi-chapi/	more controlling

Table 3: Odia derived words through reduplication

Here we can notice that every reduplication word is a repetition of a base form and every construction denotes a meaning of a single unit. Further, no affixation occurs in reduplicated forms. The reduplicated word denotes a crucial meaning which is absolutely different from the root form.

3.2. PARTIAL REDUPLICATION

Partial reduplication is a process in which a part of base form is copied. The part of base form may be a syllable, a consonant or a vowel. The copy portion is inserted word initially, finally, or medially. Further, in a reduplicated word a prefix or suffix which is not part of root form is added. For Example:

Here we can notice that the base form is not exactly reduplicated in derived word. In every word a vowel is changed. Second category of reduplication taking a suffix as described below.

- (a) /juku-jukiaa/ (firely)
- (b) /jhana-jhaniaa/ (murmuring)
- (c) /chaun-chaunaa/ (high heating condition)

- (d) /chapa-chapiaa/ (less water condition)

Here we can see that a suffix '-iaa-' is added in the final position of reduplicated word and the base form is exactly reduplicated in the derived word.

The third category of partial reduplication is seen where the part of base form is reduplicated but initial sound of base form is changed. For example:

- (a) /ghasara/ (rubbing) > /Ghasara-pasara/ (going and coming) -----repeated
- (b) /chahaka/ (glow) + /mahak/ > /chahaka-mahak/ (glowing)
- (c) /chaTa/ + /paTa/ > /chata-paTa/ (restlessness)
- (d) /chotiaa/ (small) + moTiaa (fat) > /chotia-motiaa/ (many small and something)

Here we can notice that when a base form is copied as in second word the first phoneme in base form is changed and new phoneme occurs in this position.

There are some cases where reduplication occurs in denoting opposite meaning but a negative marker (-^) is inserted in the middle stage of reduplication word; i.e.

X + (not-X) = (X-not-X). For example;

- /chuanaa/ (touchable) + (-^)+ /chuanaa/ (touchable) > /chuanaa-achuanaa/ (touchable and un-touchable)
- /Kuhaa/ (speaking) + (-^)+ /Kuhaa/ (speaking) > /kuhaa-akhuua/ (speaking and un-speaking)
- /Chirna/ (separate) + (-bi)+ /Chirna/ (separate) > /Chirna-bichirna/ (separated and un-separated)

In these data the base form is repeated exactly but a negative marker as 'a', 'n' and 'bi' are inserted in middle position for which two copies of same form in reduplication word denotes opposite meaning.

a. SPECIAL REDUPLICATION

There are some cases of reduplication of Odia where 'ku' as infix is inserted in the middle of the copying of base form. For example

- /thara/ (a chance) > /thara-ku-thara/ (many times)
- /cheka/ (phase) > /cheka-ku-cheka/ (phase to phase)
- /Jaati/ (group of) > /jaati-ki-jati/ (group to group)
- /Jodaa/ (double) > /jodaa-ku-jodaa/ (many couples)
- /Thaa/ (place) > /Thaa-ku-Thaa/ (in many places)

Here the base form copping in the derived word denotes a completely new meaning that is plurality. The insertion of 'ku' is not added with a base form but it is an infix between two copies of a base form.

b. ONOMATOPOEIA

These are not reduplication form in Odia language because some words such as: /jhan-jhan/ - (sound of object), /jhaph-jhaph/ - (sound of rain) do not denote any new meaning when the base form is reduplicated.

Secondly these are the symbolic expression of natural sound or natural human behavior. Finally they do not mark any semantic sense.

In the above classification of reduplication of Odia, we can notice many types of structure of reduplication word. In every types of reduplication word we find a process in which morphological and phonological rule are followed. Now, anyone can ask how phonology and morphology can deal with hieratical structure of reduplicated word.

There is enough literature discussing morphology and phonology of reduplication in which many linguists argue that morphology meets phonology in reduplicated construction. In other hand many argued that morphology precedes phonology. The fundamental questions in the study of reduplication are the element which is reduplicated is phonological component or morphological component? Whether, phonological rule is followed first or morphological rule.

From the data, we can see that reduplication in Odia can be formulated by three processes namely copying, vowel replacement and consonant replacement.

3.3. ECHO FORMATION & CONTRACTION

The partial repetition of a phoneme or syllable of the base may be called an echo-formation. In this process, the initial phoneme/syllable of the base is replaced by another phoneme or syllable it has neither any individual occurrence nor any meaning of its own. Here we can go through some Odia language examples for better understanding.

Noun-1	Noun-2	Echo-Formation	Gloss
/Gabesanaa/ (Research)	/Phabesanaa/ (ø)	/Gabesanaa-phabesanaa/	Research
/machi/ (fly)	/Phachi/ (ø)	/machi-phachi/	fly

However in contraction one or more syllable are dropped from the Odia root to form derived morpheme. For examples in Odia the root word, /Jagata/ (Universe) attached with a stem Naatha/ (God) in the process of contraction developed new lexeme, /Jagannatha/ whose gloss becomes 'Lord Jagannath'.

4. ODIA MORPHEME & TAGS :

A major bottleneck in developing various natural

language applications for any language is the unavailability of corresponding appropriate language resources. And for any NLP application, certain linguistic knowledge is required. Penn Treebank for English (Marcus et al., 1993), Prague Dependency Tree bank for Czech (Hajicova, 1998) etc. are some of the efforts in this direction. In the Indian languages prospective, since Indian languages are morphologically richer, they allow

the order of the words to be more flexible. This also implies that the information at the morphological level can be crucial for sentence analysis. Indian languages have a relatively free phrase-order; hence a dependency grammar based approach would be better suited for sentence analysis. So many researchers has chosen Paninian grammatical model for the input language analysis for major Indian languages.

For better illustration, here is a discussion for Odia language to extract LTAG representation from dependency structures with karaka relations. Syntactic cues like case-endings and markers such as post-positions and verbal inflections help in identifying appropriate karakas for Hindi Language.

Generally Odia sentences follow the subject, object and verb pattern. However the interchange of subject, object is acceptable. For the better illustration the Odia Treebank (OTB) we here consider the Hindi Tree Banks (HTB) (Palmer et al., 2009) for its better understanding. The OTB contains three layers: (a) dependency structure (DS), (b) Prop-Bank-style annotation (PB) for predicate-argument structure, and (c) an independently motivated phrase structure (PS) annotation which is automatically derived from the DS and from the PB. In the sentence 'Mira hathaat hasaila (Mira laughs suddenly.)' the verb 'laughs' is un-accusative in nature and it decides the subject 'Mira' as 's1'. In contrast, the PB distinct by argument predicate 'p1' is null. Whereas the third step DS-to-PS conversion process indicates the movement of object position with respect to Subject-Object-Verb syntax nature.

a. DS-Tree :

b. PB annotation :

Predicate (p1): Hathaat Hasila
S1, NP: Mira

c. PS tree :

Here PB is part of the input for the conversion process because it provides certain feature information that is not present in the DS. So 'DS+PB-to-PS' conversion" would be more complete in the case of above process.

8. CONCLUSION

Odia is a moderately synthetic language. It contains definite synthetic features, such as the bound morphemes mark tense, number (plurality), gender etc. However, though Odia language has a larger number of derivational affixes, it has virtually no inflectional morphology. Odia language has a tendency for commonly used words to have a 2:1 morpheme-word ratio i.e. on an average; there are 2 morphemes in a single word. Because of this tendency, Odia is said to "possess morphology" since almost each used word has an internal compositional structure in terms morphemes. In Odia language, generally, separate words are used to express a syntactic relationship which imparts an isolating tendency, while using inflectional morphology could have made the language more synthetic.

References :

1. Vikram Shweta, Morphology: Indian Languages and European Languages, International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications, Volume 3, Issue 6, June 2013, ISSN 2250-3153.
2. Carnie, A. 2006. Syntax: A Generative Introduction, 2nd Ed., Blackwell Publishing, United Kingdom
3. Fromkin, V. (et.al). 2011. An Introduction to Language, Wadsworth Cengage Learning,

- United States.
4. Haspelmath, M. and Sims, A. D. 2012. *Understanding Morphology*, 2nd Ed., Hodder Education.
 5. Blevins, James P., Farrell Ackerman, Robert Malouf, J. Audring & F. Masini (eds.), 'Word and Paradigm Morphology', *The Oxford Handbook of Morphological Theory*; Oxford: OUP, 2017.
 6. Mohapatra, Dhaneswar, 'Adhunika Odia Byakarana', *Kitab Mahal*, ISBN: 978-93-80360959.
 7. Penthoi, Dr. Govinda Chandra, 'A comparative study of Odia and Kui morphology', *International Journal of Applied Research* 2016; 2(9): 23-29, ISSN Online: 2394-5869.
 8. Murphy, L. M. 2010. *Lexical Meaning*, Cambridge University Press.
 9. <http://www.meertens.knaw.nl/books/synmic/abstracts/weiss.html>
 10. Naomi Sager, *Natural Language Information Processing: A Computer Grammar of English and Its Applications*, Addison-Wesley Longman Publishing Co., Inc., Boston, MA, 1981
 11. Bochner, Harry, 'Simplicity in Generative Morphology', *Publications in Language Science* 37, Mouton de Gruyter, Berlin, New York 1993, ISBN: 3110135949
 12. A Formalism for Dependency Grammar Based on Tree Adjoining Grammar, Aravind Joshi, Owen Rambow, MTT 2003, Paris, 16–18 June 2003
 13. Joshi, A. K. 2003. Tree-Adjoining Grammars. In R. Mitkov (eds.); *the Oxford Handbook of Computational Linguistics*. 483-498, Oxford University Press, New York.
 14. Arvind K. Joshi & Yves Schabes, *Tree-Adjoining Grammars*, In G. Rozenberg et al. (eds.), *handbook of Formal Languages*, Springer - Verlag Berlin Heidelberg 1997.
 15. Joshi, A. K. and K. Vijay-Shanker. 1998. Treatment of Long Distance Dependencies in LFG And TAG: Functional Uncertainty in LFG is a Corollary in TAG. *ACL '89 Proceedings of the 27th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics*, 220-227

